

A STUDY OF NOVEL AS A FORM OF LITERATURE

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Abstract

Novel is one of the most important genres of literature. Compared to other genres like poetry and drama, novel is a recent phenomenon. Though there are different opinions regarding its beginning, many scholars agree that it originated in seventeenth century. During the industrial revolution, novel became chief means of entertainment for all alike. Even today, it is most preferred genre of literature both by the readers and the writers. Therefore, this paper attempts to study the origin of novel, its elements and characteristic features and explore how it still occupies a high position among various means of entertainment available for the readers of the age of computer and internet.

Key Words: *Novel, elements, features and types of novel.*

Introduction

The dictionary meaning of the word 'novel' is 'new'. A **novel** is a "long prose narrative that describes fictional characters and events in the form of a sequential story." (<http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Novel>) In literary studies, 'Novel' is defined as "a not too unorganized, fictitious narrative in prose of at least, say 20,000 words". This definition emphasizes on the fictitiousness, plot, length and the medium of the novel. Novel is a work of art having a complex plot and long enough to allow the writer to develop various stages of the plot. That is why E.M. Forster says that a novel should be written in minimum of 50000 words.

History of the Novel:

In the history of literature, novel is a recently developed genre. There are various opinions regarding the exact year of its development. According to some scholars John Bunyan's *Pilgrim's Progress* (1678) is the first English novel. Some other scholars call Daniel Defoe's *Robinson Crusoe* (1719) as the first English novel and still some others claim Laurence Stern's *Tristram Shandy* as the first English novel. Instead of getting involved with this controversy, it is safe to say that in England novel as distinct literary genre came into existence after the industrial revolution in the 18th century.

The industrial revolution gave rise to the new middle class who wanted to have something entertaining material to spend their spare time. And to cater to the demand of these readers, many writers started writing novels. The novelists like Daniel Defoe, Samuel Richardson and Henry Fielding were trying to fulfill the increasing demand of the reading public. These writers were followed by the Bronte sisters, George Eliot, Charles Dickens and others. The great novels like Emily Bronte's *Wuthering Heights* (1847), George Eliot's *Middlemarch* (1871-72), Charles Dickens's *Great Expectations* (1816) and many others opened up new avenues of entertainment for the readers. These writers and their novels tried to fill the vacuum among the various classes of the society.

But as the time passed the readers lost their interest with this genre. The reason behind it was the availability of new means of entertainment like television, films and computers. But it doesn't mean that people have stopped writing and reading novels. On the contrary, the novel has become more popular among the readers. Even it can be said that the popularity of this genre has further increased with the rise in the field of education as it has added the newly literate readers to the existing number.

Elements of the Novel:

Plot, character, subject or theme, point of view, setting or background and style are the important elements of novel. A brief discussion of these elements will be helpful to understand novel as a form of literature.

Plot:

It is the most important element of the novel. It is called as the soul of a novel.

Plot can be defined as:

"the events that make up a story, particularly as they relate to one another in a pattern, in a sequence, through cause and effect how the reader views the story, or simply by coincidence. One is generally interested in how well this pattern of events accomplishes some artistic or emotional effect. An intricate, complicated plot is called an imbroglio, but even the simplest statements of plot may include multiple inferences, as in traditional ballads."
([http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Plot_\(narrative\)](http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Plot_(narrative)))

Plot is 'the pattern of systematic arrangement of scenes and events.' The King died and the Queen died' is a story, but 'the King died and then the Queen died of grief' is a plot.

According to Hudson, the novelist uses life as the raw material for his plot. He is concerned with passions, conflicts and ups and downs of human life. If the novelist wants his plot to be interesting and true to the life, he must be faithful to one's experiences. His novel will only then become the mirror of life. He should take material from life and present it with his creative imagination and power of narration.

The novelist takes much care for the construction of his plot. A proper attention is paid to see that all the events proceed logically and spontaneously out of each other. An ideal plot consists of a beginning, middle and an end. A good beginning is not dependent on any previous situation or background. A good middle links the beginning with its ending. A good ending is the logical outcome of what has gone before. It marks the real ending of the action and does not take it any further.

The plot can be either simple or complex. A simple plot deals with a single story whereas a complex plot deals with more than one story or episode. Sometimes the plot of a novel may be loose and incoherent or it may be compact and closely knit. The success of a novel is largely dependent on its plot.

2. Character:

As the novel deals with events and incidents taken from the real life situations, characterization is also its important element. Characters should be good, life-like and consistent. 'Life-like' means the characters must be taken from the real life situations, the men and women of flesh and blood whom we meet in our day-to-day life. Such characters remain in our memory for quite a long time. Characters can be good or bad. We may or may not love them. We like some characters and hate the others. But it should be remembered that the greatness of characters is not dependent upon whether we love or hate them. E.g. In Jane Austin's 'pride and Prejudice', Elizabeth and Darcy are good characters whereas Wickham and Lady Catherine are bad characters.

There are two methods of characterization- direct and indirect. In the direct method, the novelist himself analyzes his characters. He portrays his characters from the outside, analyzing their thoughts, feelings and behavior and provides an explanation for their behavior. In the indirect or dramatic method, the characters reveal themselves through their speech and action. The novelist is completely detached from his characters and allows them to unfold themselves through their speech and actions. Even some novelists combine the direct and the indirect method of characterization.

According to E. M. Forster, there are two types of characters - round or dynamic character and flat or static character. The round characters are those who grow and develop in the course of action. The novelist presents different stages in their growth and development. According to E.M. Forster:

“The test of a round character is whether it is capable of surprising in a convincing way. If it never surprises, it is flat. If it does not convince, it is a flat pretending to be round. It has the incalculability of life about it—life within the pages of a book.” (Forster, 19: p.49)

On the contrary, the flat characters do not grow in the course of action of the novel. They remain static throughout the action. E.g. In Thomas Hardy’s *Mayor of Casterbridge*, Michael Henchard is round character whereas Jopp is flat character.

3. Theme:

Theme is also an important element of the novel. In simple words a theme is:

“the central idea or ideas explored by a literary work. John Gardner puts it this way: “By theme here we mean not a message -- a word no good writer likes applied to his work -- but the general subject, as the theme of an evening of debates may be World Wide Inflation.” (<http://fictionwriting.about.com/od/glossary/g/theme.htm>)

If the theme of the novel is good, then it succeeds in entertaining the readers. But there is a difference between story and subject or theme of a novel. A story is a group of events in the life of character/s whereas a theme is the idea underlying the story. A theme of the novel must be really great and universal to make it successful. A great novelist does not write merely about the trivial aspects of life but he chooses the passions and conflicts of life. He chooses the subject which has universal appeal and this universality of his theme makes his novel entertaining for the readers.

4. Point of View: Point-of-view:

“Determines through whose perspective the story is viewed and narrative voice, which determines a set of consistent features regarding the way through which the story is communicated to the audience. ... The narrator may be a fictive person devised by the

author as a stand-alone entity, or may even be a character. The narrator is considered participant if an actual character in the story, and nonparticipant if only an implied character, or a sort of omniscient or semi-omniscient being who does not take part in the story but only relates it to the audience.”
(http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Narrative_mode)

A novel is nothing but the interpretation of life. An important thing in a novel is the novelist's point of view. He derives his point of view from his experiences while dealing in variety of life-situations. This may be called his philosophy of life. Great novelists have been great thinkers and keen observers of life. Yet the novelists do not deliberately express their views as they are creative writers and not the philosophers. E.g. Henry Fielding has given a panoramic commentary on England in 1745. In this novel, Fielding criticizes the domestic values which were respectfully accepted in his age.

The novelist can use either first person point of view or the third person point of view to tell his story. To tell his story, the novelist makes use of narrator. The narrator can be either a character in the novel or can be an objective observer and commentator of events. The narrator may narrate the story by using first person pronouns, 'I', 'we', or he may narrate it by using third person pronouns, 'he', 'she', 'it' and 'they'. The first person narrative technique can become lop-sided as we get only one view of the things.

The third person narrator allows the writer to keep himself away from the happenings of the novel. Such a narrator can be either partial or omniscient narrator. A partial narrator is that narrator who is present on certain events and he may narrate only those events to the readers. Whereas the omniscient narrator is present everywhere and gives us accounts of all those events. He even enters into the minds of the characters and exposes whatever is going on there.

5. Dialogue:

Dialogue is an intellectual element of the novel. It is expressed through the speech of the characters. Dialogue has the immediate relation with the characters. It is only through their dialogue we come in touch with the characters. Dialogues show the writer's technical skill.

6. Setting:

“The time, place, and circumstances in which a narrative, drama, or film takes place.” (<http://www.thefreedictionary.com/setting>) Setting means the place or location where the story of a novel takes place. It refers to the time and place in which the action of the story occurs. It includes the entire milieu of the story – the manners, customs and ways of life of the people. It also includes nature of background and environment of the age. In some novels setting is as important as the protagonist or the plot.

The novelists like Charles Dickens and Thomas Hardy give much importance to the place in their novels. For example, Hardy sets his novels in the region called Wessex. Wessex is not merely a setting in his novels but it has become a character. Same can be said about R. K. Narayan and his novels which are set in Malgudi.

The time is also an important aspect of setting. It determines the way in which various events and incidents are arranged. Some novelists follow the strict chronological sequence. But there are also some novelists, who don't pay much attention to the chronology of events. Rather they go on narrating the incidents in their novels as they occur in the minds of their narrator.

6. Style:

Style means the technique of narration. The novelists use artistic and ornamental style. He can use various figures of speech and symbols.

“Style is basically the way you write, as opposed to what you write about (though the two things are definitely linked). It results from things like word choice, tone, and syntax. It's the voice readers “hear” when they read your work.” (<http://fictionwriting.about.com/od/crafttechnique/g/style.htm>)

The author can use the technique of dialogue to develop the plot through his characters. Actually, every writer has his/her own style of writing. Some writers use a simple, straight forward style whereas some others prefer to follow their own distinctive style. In fact, style is a device a writer uses to evoke a particular tone and to create a certain atmosphere. To create the desired effect, some writers make use of repetition. They go on repeating certain words, phrases and even sentences.

The Types of Novel:

There are several types of novel. The usually accepted types of novel are:

Picaresque Novel:

The word 'picaresque' is derived from the Spanish word 'Pícaro' that means a 'rogue' or 'knave'. The picaresque novel is:

“usually a first-person narrative, relating the adventures of a rogue or low-born adventurer (Spanish pícaro) as he drifts from place to place and from one social milieu to another in his effort to survive.”
(<http://www.britannica.com/EBchecked/topic/459267/picaresque-novel>)

The Picaresque novel is a string of adventures or misadventures. It has a wandering rogue for the hero. He wanders from one place to another. He is constantly on the move in quest of adventures. A citizen of the world, he meets the people of different strata of the society. Though hardly a pattern of virtue, he often satirizes the corruptions of the aristocracy. This type of novel emphasizes only on the character of the hero.

As the hero or the heroine goes on wandering from one place to another the writer gets ample opportunity to complicate his plot by introducing numerous characters living in numerous places. And so naturally the plots of these novels become episodic in structure. Such a novel creates a realistic picture of the society.

The well-known examples of this type of novel are: Thomas Nashe's *The Unfortunate Traveler*, Cervantes' *Don Quixote*, Henry Fielding's *Tom Jones*, Daniel Defoe's *Robinson Crusoe* and Mark Twain's *The Adventures of Tom Sawyer*.

2. Psychological Novel:

The Psychological novels are also known as the 'stream of consciousness' novels. These novels deal with the workings of human psyche-conscious, subconscious and unconscious levels. This type of novels deal with the 'whatness' and the 'howness' of the mental and the spiritual experiences of the characters.

This type of novel is the outcome of the studies in the field of psychology. It helps the novelist to enter into the innermost recesses of the character's mind. As this type of novel

deals with the psyche of the characters, it lacks the chronological sequence of events. The writer freely moves from past to present and to future. Virginia Wolff's *To the Lighthouse* and *Mrs. Dalloway* and James Joyce's *Ulysses* and *The Portrait of Artist as a Young Man* are the well-known examples of psychological novel.

3. Regional Novel:

The Regional novel deals with the ordinary men and women, living in a particular locality. It describes the social and family life, customs and manners, language and culture, occupations and professions of the people of a particular region or locality. It doesn't mean that the novelist of a regional novel gives us mere photographic reproduction of the locality but he emphasizes the unique features of a particular region. And while doing so, he employs the principle of selection and ordering of material. The novelist goes on depicting the distinctive spirit of the chosen region and tries to show that life is essentially the same everywhere. This novel emphasizes the setting of a particular society. R.K. Narayan's *Swami and Friends* and Thomas Hardy's *Mayor of Casterbridge* and *Tess of the D'Urbervilles* are the well-known regional novels.

4. Gothic Novel: Gothic novel is:

"a genre of fiction characterized by mystery and supernatural horror, often set in a dark castle or other medieval setting." (<http://dictionary.reference.com/browse/gothic+novel>)

The Gothic novels were written in the latter half of 18th century. It is a story of horror. Originally the term 'Gothic' is derived from the Goths, a German tribe. Then it has come to mean 'medieval'. The Gothic novels are set against the background of medieval forts and castles. Such a setting helped the novelists to introduce supernatural elements like ghosts. The main aim of such novels was to create scenes of horror. The novelist creates the scenes in such a way that the readers are terrified to read them.

William Beckford's *Vathek* (1786) Ann Radcliff's *The Mysteries of Udolpho* (1794), Mathew Gregory Lewis' *The Monk* (1796) and Mary Shelley's *Frankenstein* (1818) are the examples of Gothic novel.

5. Epistolary Novel:

The epistolary novel “is a form in which most or all of the plot is advanced by the letters or journal entries of one or more of its characters.” (<http://www.enotes.com/epistolary-novel-essays/epistolary-novel>) The Epistolary novel is the novel in which the story is carried forward and unfolded entirely by an exchange of letters. The characters exchange their thoughts and opinions through letters. There is very little face to face dialogue. This novel was much popular in the 18th century as in those days letter was the only means of communication. Samuel Richardson’s *Pamela* (1740) and *Clarissa* (1747-48) are well known examples of epistolary novel.

6. Historical Novel:

It is one of the important types of novel. It draws its theme from some important historical event. But around this historical event the novelist weaves some imaginative and artistic environment to make it interesting. He imaginatively reconstructs the life of the past. But he does not allow historical facts to come on the way of his fiction nor does he permit his fiction to violate the significance of historical facts. Sir Walter Scott is the pioneer in this type of novel writing. George Eliot’s *Romola*, Charles Dickens’ *A Tale of Two Cities* and Thackeray’s *Henry Esmond* are some examples of this type of novel.

7. Domestic Novel:

As its name suggests, a domestic novel deals with homely life of a family preferably belonging to the middle class. It presents the day-to-day domestic life of middle class families and their friends and relatives. The usual theme of this novel is love and marriage. Jane Austen’s ‘Pride and Prejudice’ is a classic example of this type of novel. Domestic fiction is also called ‘sentimental fiction’ or ‘woman's fiction.’ It

“Refers to a type of novel popular with women readers during the middle of the nineteenth century. The genre began in the 1820s and remained a dominant fictional type until after 1870. In their reliance on the inherent goodness of human nature and the power of feelings as a guide to right conduct, these novels were in part a reaction against Calvinistic doctrines that viewed humanity as inherently depraved. (http://www.d.umn.edu/~csigler/domestic_fiction.html)

8. Prophetic Novel:

The prophetic Novels try to forecast what the future would be like. They do not claim to be absolutely correct. They only give the tentative picture of the future on the basis of the tendencies prevailing in the present.

9. Epical Novel:

An epical novel is an attempt to select and comment on those works of prose fiction in the English language that approximates to the spirit of the epic rather than to that of another literary kind. While in a tragedy there is an element of the timeless, an epic has the chronic or communal quality and is usually a mirror of the age. An epic is a narrative in verse while the novel is the narrative in prose. The novelist who succeeds in combining the epical and novelistic methods of fiction may be credited with having written an epic novel. Emile Zola is such a novelist. The examples of this type of novel are Defoe's *Robinson Crusoe* and Henry Fielding's *Tom Jones*.

In this way, all these types of novels contribute to the immense popularity of novel in the contemporary world. The complexity of themes and characters presented through novel are making it more and more interesting with every passing day.

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Internet Resources:

- <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Novel>
- [http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Plot_\(narrative\)](http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Plot_(narrative))
- <http://fictionwriting.about.com/od/glossary/g/theme.htm>
- http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Narrative_mode
- <http://www.thefreedictionary.com/setting>
- <http://fictionwriting.about.com/od/crafttechnique/g/style.htm>

<http://www.britannica.com/EBchecked/topic/459267/picaresque-novel>

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